

Sociocultural Pressure and Body Image: A Systematic Literature Review

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The impact of sociocultural pressures, including the omnipresence of media, friendships, family pressures, and the established cultural values, is a key factor in shaping body image perceptions of individuals. The systematic literature review aims to summarize and critically analyze available literature on the relationship between sociocultural pressure & body image. The review aims at establishing the common patterns, outlining the gaps in the existing body of research, and commenting on how the findings can be applied to further research programs. A systematic search based on the highly regarded databases like PubMed and Google Scholar was conducted. The search strategy included articles published in the period between 2010 and 2025 (March) and met preset inclusion and exclusion criteria. Selection criteria were based on studies that focused on the effects of media exposure, peer and cultural norms on body image in different age groups and cultural settings. Finally, 25 studies were included in the study. The results indicate that body dissatisfaction is mostly a result of sociocultural pressures. Media exposure to idealized body types, common comparisons with peers and internalized cultural ideals of beauty always turned out to be salient predictors of negative body image. Sociocultural pressures greatly affect body image in all age categories, gender, and cultural backgrounds. The study of the protective factors that can mitigate the negative effects of the sociocultural pressures should be further researched.

Keywords: Sociocultural pressure, body image, body dissatisfaction, media influence, peer influence

Body image is an important issue among the adolescent population in India, which can be explained by a set of sociocultural factors and rapid modernization. Body image refers to a psychological concept that encompasses an individual's perception and feelings regarding their own body, along with their feelings towards the bodies of other individuals (Thompson et al., 1999). Schilder (1935, 1950) defined body image as "the picture of our own body which we form in our mind that is to say, the way in which the body appears to ourselves". Body image describes how people feel and perceive their own bodies. These feelings can be perceived as either positive or negative, depending entirely on the variables affecting how that body image is perceived.

Cash (2011) argued that the concept of body image is multidimensional, meaning it encompasses multiple body images rather than just one. Many factors will have an impact on a teenager's body image; they have the influence of their parents, peers' opinions about their bodies and appearances, media influence, and even their own health issues and bodily changes that occur during puberty. Adolescents' primary source of influence is their own family members. Kostanski (2009) states that environment largely contributes to the mind set about body image. The reaction of the

family, and other acquaintances towards them and their bodies plays a vital role in developing positive or negative body image. Some even develop body dissatisfaction due to teasing and taunting from own family members (Hardit & Hannum, 2012).

A person's beliefs about their looks, feelings about their body weight, height and shape, are called body image. The four aspects to body image are: perceptual, attitudinal, cognitive and behavioral (Cash, 2011).

Perceptual Body Image

It is described as one's view about their external feature, encompassing psychological pictures about their looks (Cash, 2012). Perceptual body image refers to how we view ourselves. The way we imagine our bodies doesn't always accurately reflect our actual appearance—it's more about perception than objective reality (Cash, 2012). For instance, someone might see themselves as overweight when they are, in fact, quite thin.

Affective Body Image

It is described as feelings regarding physique including satisfaction with one's body and sense of being attractive (Pulvers et al., 2004). Clearly, our feelings are shaped by what we consume in society: the people we see on television, in films, in magazines, and, more recently, on social media. It's very important to know what kind of media we are exposed to and the effect it might have on us, whether positive or negative.

Cognitive Body Image

Cognitive parts of body image focus on the thoughts and beliefs related to how we perceive our bodies. This includes appearance schemas, misperceptions about one's own body, and the degree of mental energy invested in our appearance. Measures used to assess

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cognitive aspects include the Appearance Schema Inventory (Cash & Grasso, 2005).

Behavioural Body Image

Behavioural aspects of body image involve avoiding situations or objects that trigger concerns regarding one's body image. It also includes body-checking behaviours. To assess these aspects, various measures are utilized, including the Body Image Compulsive Action Scale (Engle, Cash, & Jarry, 2008).

Socio-cultural Pressure

Socio-cultural pressures are the actual and figurative messages in the form of beliefs, standards or choices that pressure a person to fit to the norms of the group (Cialdini et al., 2004). It stems from family, media and peers. Internalization is a key component of tripartite influence model of body dissatisfaction. According to the model, colleague, media, family cause body dissatisfaction not only direct but via two mediating mechanisms: internalizing beauty standards and socially comparing individual's personal look to that of others (Thompson et al., 1999). Furthermore, internalization works as a mediator between body dissatisfaction and social comparison (Kerry et al., 2004).

Sociocultural pressure significantly affects body dissatisfaction, particularly among young women. The internalization of societal ideals of a muscular and lean body leads to increased dissatisfaction with one's body and face (Silva et al., 2020). The media plays a crucial role and sometimes even helps to alleviate the dissatisfaction by encouraging people to engage in physical activity and pursue muscularity especially those with high socioeconomic status (Silva et al., 2020). Additionally, the social comparison and existing cultural influences play an important role in shaping the perception of obesity and body dissatisfaction, and hence influence the male and female generations (Silva et al., 2020).

Objectives of the Study

- Synthesize the existing literature that outlines the relationship

between sociocultural pressure and body image.

- Determine body image issues that are gender and culture specific.
- Explore the protective variables that alleviate the adverse effect of socio-cultural pressures.
- Highlight the common patterns, limitations and implications of the future research and intervention plans.

Method

A systematic literature review was carried out using databases like PubMed, Research Gate and Google Scholar. Articles written in English with publication dates of 2010 to March 2025 that analyzed the relationship between body image and sociocultural pressure in various ages and different cultural settings were included. The exclusion criteria included research that was not in full-text, case studies, and qualitative studies. Following the objectives of the study and the predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, a thorough search was carried out in different bibliographic repositories. Some of the keywords used were "sociocultural pressure", "body image", and "body dissatisfaction". In the course of the search, Boolean operators (like &, or, not) were used to gather relevant papers related to sociocultural pressure & body image.

Selection and Screening of the Study

Review is conducted in accordance with PRISMA statement and involved the subsequent stages.

- The preliminary inquiry generated 200 articles.
- 30 articles have been eliminated as duplicates.
- A screening process was conducted on 170 titles and abstracts.
- The inclusion/exclusion criteria led to the exclusion of 113 papers.
- 57 full-text research papers underwent a thorough evaluation.
- This led to the selection of 25 studies.

Results

Table 1

Studies on Sociocultural Pressure & Body Image

Body Image & Socio cultural Pressure				
Sr. No.	Author (Year)	Variables	Scales	Findings
1	Akbar et al. (2022)	Family-pressure Peer-pressure Media-pressure Body Image Dissatisfaction	Sociocultural Attitude toward Appearance Questionnaire (Schaefer et al., 2015) Body Dissatisfaction Scale (Schaefer et al., 2015)	The results revealed that family - pressure, media-pressure and peer-pressure all positively influence body image dissatisfaction.
2	Alburkani et al. (2024)	Body Image Social Media Eating Disorders Family influence Body Satisfaction	Body Shape Questionnaire Social Media Exposure Questionnaire Eating Attitudes Test-26 Body Attitudes subscale of the Body Investment Scale Family Influence Scale	The results revealed that 41.1% of learners face a threat for eating disorders, with 25.2% worried about body shape. Eating disorder scores negatively correlate with family influence, body satisfaction, and social media, while positively correlating with body mass index.
3	Anic et al. (2021)	Sociocultural Pressure Body Mass Index Body Image	Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 Revised Exercise Motivations Inventory-2	Women with higher BMI are more motivated to exercise for weight loss and perceive greater sociocultural pressure for an acceptable body. This pressure affects Their exercise motives and frequency.

4	Azevedo & Azevedo (2023)	Socio-Cultural Pressure Body Image	Body Appreciation Scale-2 (Lemoine et al.) Socio-cultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Scale-4 (Barra et al.) Acceptance of Cosmetic Surgery Scale (King et al.) Consumer Shopping Avoidance Behaviour Compulsive Buying Follow-up Scale (Mattos et al.)	The results revealed the influence of body image on shopping behavior and social interaction.
5	Baceviciene et al. (2023)	Body Image Sociocultural Pressure Eating Disorders	Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 Drive for Muscularity Scale Body Appreciation Scale-2 Multidimensional Self-Relations Questionnaire Appearance Scales Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire-6	The results revealed that adolescent female athletes exhibited higher purging, purgative abuse, and over physical activity than adult players. Adult males struggled with overweight and unhealthy eating more than adolescent males.
6	Chen et al. (2023)	Parental Pressure Body Image Dissatisfaction Eating Disorders	Parental Pressure subscale in the Appearance-Related Social Pressure Questionnaire Body Shape Questionnaire-14 The Eating Disorders Inventory (Garner, 1983)	Parental pressure on body image can lead to eating disorders in children. This effect varies between boys and girls and depends on puberty timing.
7	Coen et al (2024)	Parent-child relationship Media Pressure Self-Esteem Body Dissatisfaction	Body Esteem Scale for Adolescents and Adults (Mendelson et al., 2001) Pubertal Development Scale (Petersen et al., 1988) Trust subscale People in my Life Questionnaire (Cook et al., 1995) Social Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 (Schaefer et al., 2015) Self-Perception Profile for Children (Veerman et al., 1997)	Higher media pressure scores were linked to greater body dissatisfaction and lower self-esteem. Faith in parents related to low body dissatisfaction and high self-esteem, but did not reduce media pressure's impact.
8	Ellis et al. (2024)	Sociocultural pressure Body surveillance Body shame Drive for thinness Body dissatisfaction	The Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 (Schaefer et al., 2015) Objectified Body Consciousness Scale (McKinley & Hyde, 1996) Drive for Thinness Scale (Garner et al., 1983)	The results demonstrated that increased family, colleague, and media pressure leads to more body shame, drive for thinness, and body surveillance, with media pressure identified as the primary factor.
9	Eshak et al. (2020)	Body Shape Dissatisfaction Sociocultural Attitudes	Body Shape Questionnaire Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 Rosenberg Self-Esteem Questionnaire	The results revealed that about one third of students were concerned regarding their figure. BMI served the main factor of body image dissatisfaction. Family pressures affected city students, colleague influence affected village students, and both influenced students with low self-esteem.
10	Esnaola et al. (2010)	Body Image Perceived socio - cultural Pressures Body Dissatisfaction	The Questionnaire of Sociocultural Influences on the Aesthetic Body Shape Model Eating Disorder Inventory	The findings revealed that Body dissatisfaction is closely linked to sociocultural pressure. Females experience more dissatisfaction than males. Younger groups show more gender differences, and gender is a stronger predictor than age.
11	Gill & Sran (2018)	Body Dissatisfaction Sociocultural Pressure Self-esteem	Body Satisfaction Scale (Slade et al., 1990) Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire (Schaefer et al., (2015)	The results revealed that body dissatisfaction is affected by the athletic ideal, with women experiencing more than men, and is linked to socio-cultural pressures.
12	Hamid et al. (2023)	Sociocultural Influence	Body-Esteem Scale for Adults and	The results revealed that dissatisfaction

		Body Image Dissatisfaction Eating Disorders	Adolescents (Mendelson et al., 2001) Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire (Schaefer et al., (2015) Eating Attitude Test-26 (Garner et al., 1982)	with body image served a mediating role between sociocultural factors (like family, peers and media) and issues related to eating.
13	Hanson et al. (2024)	Sociocultural Pressure Body Image	Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 Demographic questions Body Appreciation Scale-2	The findings revealed that body appreciation remained consistently high among Nigerian women, while western women reported the lowest, influenced by internalized thin/athletic ideal and sociocultural pressure.
14	Izydorczyk et al. (2021)	Body Image Sociocultural Pressure Eating Disorders	The Multidimensional Body-Self Relations Questionnaire The Parental Bonding Instrument The Eating Disorder Inventory-3 Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-3	The results indicates that relationships with parents, body image concerns, and sociocultural attitudes toward appearance increase eating disorder risks. In contrast, positive parental care and body satisfaction reduce these risks.
15	Kaur et al. (2012)	Body image concern Peer influence Media influence	Peer influence Scale (Mukai, 1996) Body image concern (Mazzeo, 1999) Socio-cultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire (Heinberg et al., 1995)	The results revealed that body image concern had a positive correlation with the influence of media and peer.
16	Koscicka et al. (2016)	Body dissatisfaction Body Attitudes Body Image Perception	The Contour Drawing Rating Scale Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 The Child Figure Arrays	The study found that most children preferred thin and average body shapes over obesity. It found a strong connection between body dissatisfaction and the internalization of slender and muscular ideals, influenced by family, media, and peer pressures.
17	Mehmood et al. (2023)	Sociocultural pressure Body Dissatisfaction Body Image	Perceived Sociocultural Pressure Scale (Stice & Whitenton) Body Dissatisfaction Scale (Garner, Olmstead, & Polivy)	The results showed that perceived sociocultural pressure significantly predicts body dissatisfaction in women university students, especially urban residents. However, no significant differences were found regarding family systems or education.
18	Qasim et al. (2021)	Sociocultural Attitude Self-Esteem Body Image Dissatisfaction	Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire (Schaefer et al., (2015) Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1965) Body Dissatisfaction Scale (Tariq and Ijaz, 2015)	The findings revealed that sociocultural attitudes negatively impact body image dissatisfaction. Self-esteem negatively influences body image dissatisfaction among working women.
19	Rajagopalan & Shejwal (2014)	Body image dissatisfaction Sociocultural Pressure	Perceived Socio-cultural Pressure Scale (Stice and Agras, 1998) Demographic Sheet and BMI Young Women's Experiences with Body Weight and Shape Assessment (Delaney et al., 1997)	The findings indicate that sociocultural pressure impact body dissatisfaction through self-consciousness.
20	Shin et al. (2017)	Internalization Sociocultural Pressure BMI Body Dissatisfaction	The Korean Overall Body Esteem Scale (KOBES) (Gim & Cha, 2006) The Sociocultural Internalization of Appearance Questionnaire (Thompson et al., 2004) The Leisure-Time Exercise Questionnaire Sociocultural Influences on Body Image and Body Change Questionnaire (McCabe	The results revealed that media pressure had the most significant effect on adopting the slender standard, leading to body dissatisfaction, followed by pressures from peers and parents, which also influenced body image.

21	Silva et al. (2020)	Body Image Sociocultural pressure Body Dissatisfaction	And Ricciardelli, 2001) Body Area Scale Revised (Lerner et al) Sociocultural Attitudes Toward Appearance Questionnaire-(Schaefer et al.) Sociodemographic Questionnaire	The results showed that women's dissatisfaction with their bodies and faces rises due to sociocultural pressure and the desire for a slim figure. Media influences, economic status and physical activity also affect these attitudes. Higher BMI links to greater dissatisfaction.
22	Soohinda et al. (2020)	Body Image Dissatisfaction Sociocultural Pressure	Mini International Personality Item Pool (MINI-IPIP) Personality Scale Rosenberg's Self- Esteem Scale Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 Body Shape Questionnaire (BSQ-8c)	The results revealed that 34.44% of the 500 males had moderate to marked Body Image Dissatisfaction. Underweight men showed more BID than obese men. BID was linked to neuroticism.
23	Stojcic et al. (2020)	Body Image Dissatisfaction Sociocultural Pressure	Contour Rating Scale (Thompson & Gray, 1995) Body Area Scale (Lerner et al., 1973) Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 (Schaefer et al., (2015) Body Mass Index	The results showed that thin internalization predicted body image dissatisfaction in Chinese and Croatian samples. Chinese women experienced more dissatisfaction and higher thin-ideal internalization than Croatian women, along with more pressure to meet beauty standards. They also had a negative view of their body size. Chinese men preferred thinner women, while both groups misjudged women's preferences for body size.
24	Tanguay et al. (2025)	Body Image Appearance-related Pressure Eating behaviour	Intuitive Eating Scale-2 (Carbonneau et al., 2016; Tylka & Van Diest, 2013) Body Esteem Scale (Mendelson et al., 2001) Body Dissatisfaction subscale from the Eating Disorder Inventory-3 Questionnaire for girls (Garner, 2004) The Body Dissatisfaction subscale from the Eating Disorder Assessment for Men (Stanford & Lemberg, 2012) Sociocultural Attitudes Towards Appearance Questionnaire-4 (Rodgers et al., 2016)	The results revealed that Generalized-Pressure group showing the poorest relationship with food and body image.
25	You & Shin (2020)	Sociocultural Influences Drive for Thinness Drive for Muscularity Body Dissatisfaction	Leisure-Time Exercise Questionnaire (LTEQ) Body Dissatisfaction subscale of the Eating Disorder Inventory (EDI-BD) Drive for Muscularity Scale (DMS) Drive for Thinness subscale of the Eating Disorder Inventory (EDI-DFTS) Tripartite Influence Scale	The results showed that media pressures have the greatest effects on body dissatisfaction and ideals. Gender differences exist in the association between sociocultural pressures and body dissatisfaction.

Discussion

The results of this systematic literature review indicate the effect of sociocultural pressures, which includes media, family, and peers, on one's body image perceptions and body image related behaviors. Across the 25 studies reviewed, a clear trend was observed which indicate the relationship between higher exposure to sociocultural standards of beauty and increased body dissatisfaction, particularly among adolescents and young adults.

The influence of media has been identified as the primary factor

affecting body image issues. Ellis et al. (2024), Shin et al. (2017), and You and Shin (2020) highlighted that the internalization of ideals promoted by media, whether thin or muscular, leads to body image dissatisfaction. Social media contributes to an increased likelihood of comparing oneself with others and idealizing unrealistic ideals related to appearance. The dynamics within a family are important as poor self-esteem, eating disorders and diminished body image are strongly linked to parental pressure and critical remarks about appearance (Chen et al., 2023).

According to the majority of research, women are more likely than

men to be dissatisfied with their bodies and to feel pressure from society to maintain a slim figure (Esnaola et al., 2010; Stojcic et al., 2020). In addition, the review also points out that men are becoming more worried, especially about muscularity and fitness ideals (Soohinda et al., 2020).

Cultural context significantly influences sociocultural pressure. In the Asian context, the cultural values of appearance and collectivism, combined with family expectations, have served to shape the nature of sociocultural pressure. Chinese participants experienced more dissatisfaction and higher thin-ideal internalization than Croatian (Stojcic et al., 2020). Overall, the results show that, due to global media, beauty standards are increasingly convergent across cultural boundaries.

Although empirical studies pay a lot of attention to risk factors, many studies have found examples of protective variables capable of mitigating the effect of the sociocultural pressure. These are body appreciation, strong self-esteem, development of relationships with parents, and increased concern with appearance and involvement in physical activity to gain health benefits and not to merely gain body attractiveness. The findings indicate that the enhancement of a positive body image and resilience can be more effective than just monitoring the risk factors.

The results highlight the need for interventions on various levels. To the individual, internalization and social comparison can be countered by increasing media literacy and using cognitive-behavioural techniques. In the family and school settings, the creation of body-positive space is crucial and comments on appearance should be avoided. At a larger social level, the societal policies are needed to deal with unrealistic media images, endorse a variety of body images, and fight against weight-based stigma.

There are number of shortcomings in the literature available. First, there is the issue of causation because most of the designs are based on cross-sectional designs. Second, the emphasis on females has limited the knowledge of males. Third, the majority of the samples include adolescents and emerging adults, and little research is available on children and older adults. Also, the lack of research on non-western populations exists.

Longitudinal and experimental studies should be emphasized in future research so as to establish cause-effect relationships. The effects of the emerging digital platforms on body-image perceptions should also be investigated, including filters and AI-generated images. Future research on protective factors and frameworks that enable a positive body image and intersectional research that considers diverse social identities is still extremely necessary.

Conclusion

This review shows that sociocultural pressure is a significant predictor of body image dissatisfaction in a wide range of genders, ages & cultural background. Although media has been the most extensive source of this pressure, friends and family are also crucial in influencing the self-perception, mostly through the process of internalization and comparison. How different people perceive and react to these pressures differs significantly according to gender and culture. Sociocultural determinants must be addressed to develop a healthier body image and prevent mental health complications, which should be achieved by educating, reforming policies, providing a favourable family environment, and responsible media practices.

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